

Managing The Entrepreneurial Stress of Young Entrepreneurs: The Roles of Family Support, Family Cohesion, and Locus of Control

Uzoma Heman Ononye Ph.D.*, Dumebi Ezar Ehigiator

¹Department of Business Management
Dennis Osadebay University, Delta State, Nigeria

²Independent Researcher/Hadassah Hall Group of Schools

Email Address

¹Heman.ononye@dou.edu.ng, ²Dezarpet@yahoo.com

* Corresponding Author

Abstract: *Entrepreneurship is a stressful activity that can impede normal functioning. The study investigated the effect of family support on entrepreneurial stress, considering the moderating roles of family cohesion and locus of control. 156 registered SMEs in Delta State, Nigeria, provided the cross-sectional data for this quantitative study. Results from the partial least squares analysis show that family support significantly reduces entrepreneurial stress. Furthermore, family cohesion had a significant negative moderating effect, and locus of control had an insignificant negative moderating effect in the family support and entrepreneurial stress nexus. Based on the findings, the study concluded that family support had a beneficial negating effect on entrepreneurial stress, with family cohesion and locus of control playing significant and less significant roles, respectively. Therefore, the study recommends that entrepreneurs should receive education on the protective roles of family in entrepreneurship, particularly in mitigating stress and its detrimental effects on young entrepreneurs. This knowledge will help them during their formative stage to build their bond and elicit more supportive resources as the relationship improves. Secondly, young entrepreneurs should participate in upskilling entrepreneurship programmes to enhance their internal control capabilities over stress-inducing situations. Thirdly, entrepreneurs should strengthen their relationships through effective communication, shared experiences, and active involvement in meaningful family traditions and activities. This approach is critical for elevating the level of family cohesiveness.*

Keywords: Entrepreneurial stress, family support, family cohesion, locus of control

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is a challenging activity characterised by high risks, uncertainties, and complexities when starting and running a successful business. This evolving pressure exposes individuals to a myriad of stressors (work overload, role conflict, time pressures, long working hours, financial insecurity, and economic uncertainty) that can interfere with normal functioning and effectiveness in the entrepreneurial role. Entrepreneurs experience more stress than non-entrepreneurs because they carry the burden for the success and survival of their businesses in a highly competitive environment (Barbosa et al., 2024). Arguably, stress is inextricably linked to the entrepreneurial process, making entrepreneurs a vulnerable group of individuals. This challenge makes it important to identify ways to ameliorate the manifestations of entrepreneurial stress. Against this backdrop, this study selects family support, locus of control, and family cohesion to bring attention and clarity to the psychological aspects of entrepreneurial behaviours. Family support is any form of instrumental, informational, and emotional assistance provided to an entrepreneur by family members. Family cohesion is the shared emotional bond among family members. Locus of control is the personal belief that one can control events affecting his or her behaviours and actions.

The construct of family support is important because family characteristics and dynamism create an atmosphere of relief and recovery from stressful situations (Ugwu et al., 2019). Entrepreneurial behaviours often occur in the context of family relationships, existing career opportunities, and economic conditions (Hibrecht, 2016). This

statement implies that entrepreneurs rely on social groups, such as family, to assist them in surmounting the challenges associated with the entrepreneurial process (Kipkosgei, 2022). Based on the job demand-control-support (JDCS) framework, stress stems from poor support, little control, and high expectations or demands (Bajaba et al., 2022). This framework suggests that family support and locus of control are critical to entrepreneurs because it provides opportunities for them to manage the stressors they face, thereby aiding adaptability and stress reduction to support their psychological wellbeing and health.

Research (Uddin, 2021; Ononye, 2022) indicates that individuals who are happier, hard-working, and committed are better equipped to manage stress and are more likely to receive more social support than those who are not. This belief stems from their ability to execute activities that influence the results and support they receive. Given that family resources are stretched due to competing demands from family members, one's internal locus of control in their entrepreneurial careers may influence the quality of support they receive from family members. It is necessary to consider individual attributes such as locus of control, as entrepreneurs operate independently based on their disposition. However, while evidence for stress reduction across professions is inconsistent, a consistently highlighted protective factor relates to an individual's control perception (Güzel et al., 2024). An entrepreneur's locus of control is likely to shape their cognitive, emotional, and behavioural reactions to resources and situations. Internal locus of control orientation enhances positive thinking, help-seeking, adaptive functioning, and other problem-focused behaviors. The development of this relatively stable resource prevents resource loss and fosters resource gain in response to stressful experiences. The buffering effect of control capabilities on the cognitive perception and behavioural outcomes relationship has been documented in Abdullah et al. (2021). Andiyasari et al. (2017) pointed out that it is important to determine how personal factors and contextual factors relate and influence individual behavior. Therefore, how family support and one's locus of control interact to reduce entrepreneurial stress warrants investigation, as studies have not yet fully established this relationship in this context (Karimi & Alipour, 2011).

Additionally, there are conditions where family support significantly reduces the stress level of entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs tend to spend a greater part of their lives at work. There is usually no clear distinction between work and family lives, with irritability, fatigue, burnout, and other stress-induced symptoms spilling over into the family domain (Grant & Ferris, 2012). These spillovers have a way of generating tension among members, ultimately leading to conflict. Ononye et al. (2022) argue that families can differentially support their members engaged in entrepreneurship, with some obtaining and others not securing the necessary resources for optimal functioning. Arguably, the quality and quantity of family support can vary in strength according to the level of family cohesion. According to Agrawal and Mahajan (2022), when cohesiveness among family members increases, work-family conflict reduces and family work enrichment improves to the extent that the individual would see a boost in his or her psychological health. As such, family cohesion can create conditions that enable the effectiveness of social support in attenuating stress among young entrepreneurs. Research has highlighted family cohesion as a significant moderator that protects individuals in the management of stress (Ugwu et al., 2019).

Recently, Kiefl et al. (2024) proposed that studies should focus more on how entrepreneurs manage stressful work conditions to ensure sustainable and successful business. We bring this consideration to young entrepreneurs, who are in the early stages of their development, facing strong competition from more established entrepreneurs who have prior experience and strategic resources in a highly turbulent and disruptive economic environment. Scholars suggest that many new businesses do not survive beyond five years, and this phenomenon is attributed to factors associated with the newness of an individual to entrepreneurship (Forde, 2021). They have to build on their initial and limited experiences by learning to deal with different, specific problems and disruptions to entrepreneurial activities. This learning curve disadvantage creates stressful situations as entrepreneurs often find themselves in unfamiliar terrain. It is likely young entrepreneurs will initially struggle in managing stress because they face high work demands they may not be fully prepared for and may find it difficult to cope if the demands exceed their motivation and coping abilities. The study's objectives are as follows:

- (i) To determine the effect of family support on entrepreneurial stress.
- (ii) To study whether locus of control moderates the effect of family support on entrepreneurial stress.
- (iii) To ascertain how family cohesion moderates the effect of family support on entrepreneurial stress.

Literature Review

Family Support and Entrepreneurial Stress

Family support refers to how an entrepreneur perceives the assistance obtained from familial relations, such as parents, siblings, cousins, aunts, uncles, etc. This assistance can be expressed instrumentally or emotionally and is offered in variable contexts because of an inherent sense of obligation, duty and responsibility, and reciprocity within the family (Ononye et al., 2022). Instrumental support is the perceived tangible and practical assistance (e.g., provision of capital, information sharing, and help with different tasks and assignments) to help solve problems. On the other hand, emotional support is the affective expressions (e.g., care, encouragement, empathy, and active listening) received from family members. The premise of family support is that people in close relationships assist or help one another achieve personal goals in different ways. This help provides motivational resources that enable them to have better self-control over certain situations, facilitating the stability of their psychological well-being and health through the rigours of the entrepreneurial process. Entrepreneurs are embedded in a social system of exchange relationships, and as a consequence, their behaviours are influenced by the quality of the social exchange ties they develop over time (Ononye, 2022). Family support is important in entrepreneurial adaptation considering the initial challenges in developing strong social support system for young entrepreneurs. Family networks offers support that would otherwise have been unavailable to the entrepreneur. According to Buttner (1992:224), “stress is a function of discrepancies between one’s expectations and one’s ability to meet demands and discrepancies between the individual’s expectations and his/her personality.” When an entrepreneur is unable to meet his or her role demands and expectations, stress occurs. The sources of stress include but are not limited to role conflict, role ambiguity, role overload, responsibility pressure, concern for quality, and work-family conflict. These stressors lead to negative emotions, job dissatisfaction, and poor psychological health among entrepreneurs. Krithiga and Velmurugan (2024) found that an entrepreneur’s performance quality is related to his or her ability to manage stress stemming from the different stressors associated with their role. Stress levels are likely to increase as the probability and proximity of business failure increase (Williams, 1985). Young entrepreneurs’ lack of entrepreneurial knowledge and insufficient resources make them highly vulnerable to stress.

Entrepreneurs with a high level of job stress receive more family support because they may solicit more and because their family offered more support to protect them from mental and emotional fatigue. Family support may be more necessary for stressful roles, like entrepreneurship, than for less stressful roles. However, job stress could predict the nature and quality of family support (Wu et al., 2020; Kaur, 2024). Using a sample of employees in wineries in New York, Brannon and Wiklund (2016) found that social support is a preventive resource that protects people from perceiving stress. Gao et al. (2020) demonstrated that social support influenced job satisfaction and performance directly and indirectly through job stress reduction among employees working in the Vietnamese banking sector. Uddin (2020) found that family social support provides valuable resources for female employees, particularly working mothers, in the banking and healthcare professions to handle stressful work settings during periods of heightened uncertainty, such as the pandemic. Liu’s (2022) study discovered that practical and emotional assistance from friends and families is a germane form of social support for mothers working shifts to cope with their work stress in Mexican casinos. The reviewed studies paid little attention to family support in the entrepreneurial context, as the focus has been on working mothers and other employees who engage in a non-entrepreneurial role. However, family support significantly and positively contributes to entrepreneurial well-being (Huang et al., 2024), and this can be accomplished by decreasing the perceived level of stress (Acoba, 2024). Therefore, the study hypothesises that:

H₁: Family support significantly reduces entrepreneurial stress.

Moderation of Locus of Control

Locus of control refers to a generalised belief or attitude about the nature of the causal relationship between an entrepreneur’s own behaviour and its outcomes. Individuals who believe that the outcomes attained are directly or partly from their efforts and actions possess an internal locus of control, while those believing that outcomes are externally influenced and outside their control have an external locus of control. Individuals with an external locus of control perceive themselves in a passive role and are not as confident, motivated, and alert in attempting to control their environment (Thomas et al., 2006). Entrepreneurs will have little motivation to act or be self-directed in the pursuit of opportunities unless they believe in their abilities to foster desired results and reduce undesirable ones through their behaviour. Tseng et al. (2022) suggested that individuals with a high internal locus of control want others to perceive them as willing and capable of managing challenges associated with entrepreneurship. Hence, they tend to elicit related assistance from people in their social networks, including

family, to reinforce actions for positive change. Importantly, entrepreneurs with a high external locus of control can attribute blame and responsibilities to the environment (i.e., family) for the consequences of personal actions. A high internal locus of control helps reduce stress (Chen & Silverthorne, 2008). Vanderzee et al. (2006) suggested that people who have more internal control beliefs perceive more support from their social networks than people with an external control belief. It shows that entrepreneurs with an internal locus of control are better equipped to handle challenges that come their way and not leave their situation to luck or fate. They take decisions with a sense of responsibility and duty to a given role and, as such, may attract rewards or outcomes that will make them persist amid challenges. Micheletto et al. (2022) stated that a high locus of control modulates the personal resources achieved through personal growth and perceived happiness in uncertain working environments. It is plausible to say that a family may feel comfortable assisting its members who exude personal resources (creativity, confidence, autonomy, commitment, and a positive attitude towards stressful events) attributable to their entrepreneurial growth and positive mood towards life events. Mahmoud et al. (2021) noted that locus of control buffers psychosocial reactions, such as stress, making individuals less susceptible to them. Based on a sample of bankers in Vietnam, Giao et al. (2020) found that individuals with an internal locus of control have low work stress, and it also conditions the social support and work stress nexus. Consequently, the second hypothesis was proposed.

H₂: The interaction between locus of control and family support significantly reduces entrepreneurial stress.

Moderation of Family Cohesion

Family cohesion refers to the emotional or psychological bonding that underlies family members and their degree of autonomy. The primary objective is to help in tasks that impact family members, thereby improving their well-being, functioning, and adaptation of the family to new situations and needs. Nurlaily et al. (2018) indicate that supportive actions are embedded in the emotional ties of family members and in the structure of family networks. The emotional bonds determined by family cohesion can easily sustain the quality, quantity, and frequency of support required by an entrepreneur in his/her entrepreneurial endeavours. Family cohesion, a protective factor, is intricately related to self-identity and resilience, which are developed when family relationships are robust and strong. It is important for self-development because it promotes warmth, nurture, encouragement, affection, emotional expressions, and mutual concern for personal growth. These elements are crucial for the mental development of an individual. Edelman et al. (2016) suggest that family cohesion can moderate the influence of family support and enhance the scope of entrepreneurial activities. Even though family cohesion reduces stress (Zeng et al., 2021), studies show it can also help moderate relationships involving stress and other related psychological factors (Ugwu et al., 2019; Stevenson et al., 2021).

H₃: The interaction between family cohesion and family support significantly reduces entrepreneurial stress.

Theoretical Framework

Conservation of Resources Theory

This study was grounded in the conservation of resources (COR) theory, which posits that entrepreneurs develop and protect their essential personal resources to mitigate the risk of actual resource loss while promoting resource gain. In demanding work contexts, resource depletion often occurs, leading individuals to seek practical ways for replenishment to prevent stress. Stress manifests when job demands outweigh the available job resources. This scenario necessitates leveraging one's social support system to obtain resources that can restore normal functioning. In this context, family support, comprising informational, practical, and emotional assistance, is important for young entrepreneurs with limited initial resources, which often become depleted as they face new situational contexts and circumstances. However, entrepreneurs with strong family cohesion may secure the desired support to effectively manage stress amid changes within the entrepreneurial environment. Furthermore, a high locus of control may be important because family members are more inclined to offer limited support when they perceive the individual as capable of utilising it effectively. Both family cohesion and locus of control create protective conditions that cause family support to be effective in reducing the likelihood of prolonged or transient stress. They also ensure assistance from family members is sustained.

The proposed hypotheses (H₁ – H₃) were put together in Figure 1, showing that family support significantly reduces entrepreneurial stress under high locus of control and family cohesion.

Figure 1: The Research Model
Source: Developed by the Researchers, 2025

Methodology

The study employed the cross-sectional research design by using a structured questionnaire developed from related studies' validated measurement scales. It purposively sampled respondents who have been in business for no more than five (5) years and had no entrepreneurial experience prior to starting the business, as this study was on early-stage (or young) entrepreneurs. The selection of SMEs in Delta State was due to their proximity, which allows for a more focused investigation. A sample of 158 was obtained from a population of 261 registered SMEs in Delta State using Yamane's formula. Simple random sampling was applied to guarantee an equal chance of selection. The study was conducted for two months, commencing in February and concluding in March 2025. The respondents were presented with a cover letter outlining the study's objectives and the participants' rights. Participation in this study was voluntary. Two assistants facilitated the administration and collection of the questionnaires. A total of 156 usable questionnaires were collected. The demographic profile indicates that the sample comprised 65 males and 91 females, with a mean age and experience of 33.8 and 3.9 years, respectively. 78 had a bachelor's degree, 45 had a diploma certificate, 20 had a senior school certificate, and 13 had a postgraduate degree.

The questionnaire utilised validated scales of prior studies for its development and had a total of eighteen (18) questions. It was also rated on a five-point Likert scale. The study adapted four (4) questions on family support from the works of Edelman et al. (2016) and Kipkosgei (2022). A sample question is, "I can find help from family members." Duradoni et al. (2021) provided the locus of control scale comprising five (5) questions. A sample question is, "I strive to achieve my goals." The four-item measurement scale for family cohesion was obtained from Edelman et al.'s (2016) study. A sample item is, "Family togetherness is important." Fatoki (2019) provided the five (5) questions used to assess entrepreneurial stress. A sample statement is, "I have a heavy workload every day."

A pre-test of the questionnaire was conducted to verify its quality. A professor of strategic management and entrepreneurship, along with two entrepreneurs from the target population, were consulted to validate the questionnaire at face value. The appropriateness, conciseness, clarity, and comprehension of the question items were confirmed by them. We administered the questionnaire to 15 respondents to assess its construct reliability. The SPSS 20 software aided the Cronbach alpha test. The test results indicated that family support (0.757), locus of control (0.783), family cohesion (0.801), and entrepreneurial stress (0.794) had scores that exceeded the cut-off point of 0.70. According to Hair et al. (2022), scores above 0.70 suggest adequate internal consistency among the constructs, thus confirming acceptable construct reliability.

The partial least squares modelling (PLSM) approach was selected for data analysis and testing of hypotheses. The PLSM is a widely used structural equation modelling method that imposes fewer restrictions on sample size and can achieve stable estimations when the hypothesised model include contextual variables. The study adhered to the procedure and guidelines recommended by Hair et al. (2022) for data analysis, hypothesis testing, and result interpretation. The SmartPLS 4 software aided the PLSM analysis.

Results and Discussion of Findings

The study used the two-step method outlined by Hair et al. (2022) to first check if the measurement model is reliable and valid and then to evaluate the structural model to see if the proposed relationships hold true. A

preliminary test using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure [KMO] and Bartlett's test for sphericity [BTS] was done to confirm the factorability of the data. This initial test was aided by the SPSS 20 software. The KMO values for family support, locus of control, family cohesion, and entrepreneurial stress were 0.690, 0.717, 0.733, and 0.795, respectively. With an acceptable benchmark score of 0.60, the data was considered adequate for factor analysis. The BTS scores for all the constructs were all significant at $p < 0.05$, suggesting the variances explained by the dataset were suitable for factor analysis. Based on these results, the study tested the measurement model. In table 1, the factor loadings were above the cut-off threshold of 0.707, suggesting good item reliability was attained. The items correlated well with their respective constructs. Construct reliability was achieved through the composite reliability, given that the score exceeded the minimum acceptable limit of 0.70.

Additionally, the AVE scores for all the constructs were higher than the permissible limit of 0.50, suggesting the constructs correlated well and strongly with each other. The correlation values of each construct (bolded values) were higher than their correlations with other constructs (non-bolded values), indicating that discriminant validity met the Fornell-Larcker criterion. The variance inflation factor (VIF) measures how highly correlated the constructs are, and values not more than 5 show a lack of significant multicollinearity problems (Hair et al., 2022). According to Kock (2015), scores below 3.3 show the absence of significant concern for common method bias. The VIF values were below 5 for multicollinearity and below 3.3 for common method bias, suggesting no related problems. Given the above, the acceptable values in the selected quality criteria show that the measurement model is both valid and reliable.

Table 1. Measurement Model Results

Constructs	1	2	3	4
1. Family support	0.715			
2. Locus of control	0.158	0.739		
3. Family cohesion	0.201	0.322	0.735	
4. Entrepreneurial stress	-0.247	-0.225	-0.118	0.752
Mean	3.567	3.945	4.117	3.784
Standard deviation	0.861	0.994	0.683	1.276
FL (> 0.707)	0.854 – 0.909	0.770 – 0.819	0.745 – 0.824	0.787 – 0.805
CR (> 0.70)	0.740	0.817	0.799	0.784
AVE (> 0.50)	0.533	0.609	0.596	0.641
VIF	1.870	1.275	1.944	

Note: AVE = average variance extracted, CR = factor loads, FL = factor loads, SRMR = standardized root mean square residual, VIF = variance inflation factor

Table 2. Structural Model Results

Path (Hypothesis)	β (p-value)	Decision
1. FS → ES	-0.237 (0.000)	Accept
2. LoC*FS → ES	-0.091 (0.188)	Reject
3. FC*FS → ES	-0.103 (0.031)	Accept
R²	0.346	

Note: FS = family support, LoC = locus of control, FC = family cohesion
ES = entrepreneurial stress, $p < 0.05$

The predictive quality of the structural model was determined by R². According to Chin et al. (2008), values between 0.33 and 0.66 are considered moderate. The R² result shows that family support and its interaction with locus of control and family cohesion moderately explain 34.6% of the changes in entrepreneurial stress. H₁ states that family support significantly reduces entrepreneurship, and the PLSM result ($\beta = -0.237$; $p = 0.000$) confirms this argument holds true. Therefore, families can reduce the perceived stress levels of their members involved in entrepreneurship by extending and increasing their support, helping them thrive and be productive. For young entrepreneurs, family support is crucial to their psychological stability given that they possess limited experience and resources. Family support may be the first point of call as they look to extend their social capital to include other categories of individuals. This finding is consistent with prior studies (Uddin, 2020; Liu, 2022) that reported family support ameliorates work stress. In some ways, it supports researchers who discovered a negative

correlation between social support and job stress (Brannon & Wiklund, 2016; Giao et al., 2020). Given that these studies were in a non-entrepreneurial context, the study highlights the relevance of family support for stress reduction among entrepreneurs. As Huang et al. (2024) state, family support is crucial to entrepreneurial wellbeing, of which improvement is a result of a decline in the level of stress that one perceives or experiences.

H₂ proposes that the interaction between locus of control and family support significantly reduces entrepreneurial stress, and the PLSM result ($\beta = -0.091$; $p = 0.188$) refutes this statement. Thus, H₂ was not accepted. Although the moderation of locus of control facilitated family support attenuation of stress, the reduction in stress levels was not significant. It is possible that entrepreneurs with a high internal locus of control may not rely on family support to get things done, as they believe the situation is within their control and they can develop distinctive resources to effectively navigate stressful and challenging situations. The belief in their personal resources and efforts makes it possible for them to require little assistance from family members. Another possible reason is that locus of control moderates certain types of support. Entrepreneurs with a high internal locus of control are adept at finding and using information for problem-solving, learning, and adapting. They may find some supports more useful than others, especially when they align with their personal motivation and goals. This finding contradicts Vanderzee et al. (2006) and Mahmoud et al. (2021), who reported that internal control beliefs buffer psychosocial reactions to the point that they perceive more social support and persist in the entrepreneurial role. The finding disagrees with Giao et al. (2020), who stated that an internal locus of control conditions the social support and work stress nexus significantly.

H₃ states that the interaction between family cohesion and family support significantly reduces entrepreneurial stress, and the PLSM result ($\beta = -0.103$; $p = 0.031$) supported this statement. Thus, H₃ was accepted. The supportive conditions created by family cohesion are important in limiting the perceived stress levels among young entrepreneurs. Families may offer assistance to members who have a strong familial connection to leverage. When family cohesion is high, members cooperate rather than compete for supportive resources that are often severely stretched with competing demands (Igwe et al., 2018). This finding confirms the position of Edelman et al. (2016) that family cohesion modulates family support's ability to enhance the scope of entrepreneurial activities in stressful environments. It also agrees with prior studies (Ugwu et al., 2019; Stevenson et al., 2021) that operationalised family cohesion as a moderating factor in relationships involving stress and reported its importance in attenuating stress levels among individuals. Based on the theoretical foundations of this study, it confirmed the arguments drawn from the COR theory, stating that family support allows entrepreneurs to receive and access resources that assist in managing stress-inducing events and situations. However, there are other protective operational conditions that help entrepreneurs to amplify how family support controls stress levels. Stress reduction was facilitated by the presence of locus of control and family cohesion, with the latter being significant within the study's model.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the family support and entrepreneurial stress nexus by accounting for the contextual influences of locus of control and family cohesion among young entrepreneurs. The study found that family support significantly reduces entrepreneurial stress. However, while both locus of control and family cohesion contribute to lowering the perceived stress levels among entrepreneurs, the former was considered significant within the study's model. Based on the conservation of resources theory, the study concluded that family support had a beneficial negating effect on entrepreneurial stress, with family cohesion and locus of control playing significant and less significant roles, respectively. Therefore, the study recommends that:

1. Entrepreneurs should receive education on the protective roles of family in entrepreneurship, particularly in mitigating stress and its detrimental effects on young entrepreneurs. This knowledge will help them during their formative stage to build their bond and elicit more supportive resources as the relationship improves. It is important to discuss these findings in skill acquisition and entrepreneurship training programmes because entrepreneurial development is everyone's concern, including families.
2. Young entrepreneurs should participate in upskilling entrepreneurship programmes to enhance their internal control capabilities over stress-inducing situations. Conducting a personality assessment enables targeted interventions in areas of weakness.
3. Entrepreneurs should strengthen their relationships through effective communication, shared experiences, and active involvement in meaningful family traditions and activities. This is because a cohesive family, characterized by high emotional bonds, can provide supportive context for the entrepreneurial development of members in stressful situations.

The study is not without limitations. The study's geographic coverage was limited, as it was conducted in a single state in Nigeria. Future studies should extend to other Nigerian states to better the generalisability of the results. The study relied on cross-sectional data, which may not fully elucidate causal relationships. Researchers should consider using mixed data (triangulation data) and longitudinal data to add depth to the study's inferences. The study focused on moderators affecting the family support and entrepreneurial stress nexus. Given that the study's model moderately explains the variations in stress, future research should include mediators, such as positive affect, psychological capital, etc., to develop a more comprehensive framework. Family support is a multidimensional construct comprising instrumental, informational, and emotional aspects; as such, the study was unable to specify the support dimension(s) that influenced entrepreneurial stress. Researchers should consider their distinct effects in their studies.

References

- Acoba, E. F. (2024). Social support and mental health: the mediating role of perceived stress. *Frontiers in Psychology, 15*, 1330720. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1330720>
- Abdullah, H., Ismail, I., Alnoor, A., & Yaqoub, E. (2021). Effect of perceived support on employee's voice behaviour through the work engagement: A moderator role of locus of control. *Int. J. Process Management and Benchmarking, 11*(1), 60–79. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJPMB.2021.112253>
- Andiyasari, A., Riantoputra, C. D., & Matindas, R. W. (2017). Voice behavior: The role of perceived support and psychological ownership. *The South East Asian Journal of Management, 11*(1), 1–24.
- Agrawal, M., & Mahajan, R. (2022). The relationship between family cohesion, family-work conflict, enrichment and psychological health of Indian police. *Policing an International Journal, 45*(5), 794–811. <https://doi.org/10.1108/pijpsm-02-2022-0028>
- Bajaba, S., Azim, M. T., & Uddin, M. A. (2022). Social support and employee turnover intention: Mediating role of Work-Family Conflict. *Review of Business Management, 24*(1), 48–65. <https://doi.org/10.7819/rbgn.v24i1.4153>
- Barbosa, R. M. A., Pérez-Nebra, A. R., Villajos, E., & González-Ladrón-De-Guevara, F. (2024). The entrepreneur's well-being: current state of the literature and main theories. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research, 14*(1), 46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40497-024-00413-4>
- Brannon, L. D., & Wiklund, J. (2016). An analysis of business models: firm characteristics, innovation and performance. *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal, 22*(1), 1–20.
- Buttner, E. H. (1992). Entrepreneurial Stress: Is it Hazardous to Your Health? *Journal of Managerial Issues, 4*(2), 223–240.
- Chen, J., & Silverthorne, C. (2008). The impact of locus of control on job stress, job performance and job satisfaction in Taiwan. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal, 29*(7), 572–582. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437730810906326>
- Chin, W. W., Peterson, R. A., & Brown, S. P. (2008). Structural equation modeling in marketing : Some practical reminders structural equation modeling in marketing: Some practical reminders. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice, 16*(4), 287–298. <https://doi.org/10.2753/MTP1069-6679160402>
- Duradoni, M., Salvatori, G., Meacci, S., Panerai, G., & Guazzini, A. (2021). Development and validation of the Internet Locus of Control Scale (I-LOC). *New Media & Society, 25*(6), 1227–1247. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448211019495>
- Edelman, L. F., Manolova, T., Shirokova, G., & Tsukanova, T. (2016). The impact of family support on young entrepreneurs' start-up activities. *Journal of Business Venturing, 31*(4), 428–448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2016.04.003>
- Fatoki, O. (2019). Entrepreneurial stress, burnout, intention to quit and performance of Immigrant-Owned small businesses in South Africa. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship, 23*(4), 1–15. 1-5.
- Forde, W. (2021). Strategies to improve the survival rate beyond 5 years for small business in Guyana. *Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies, 11071*. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/11071>
- Giao, H. N. K., Vuong, B. N., & Tushar, H. (2020). The impact of social support on job-related behaviors through the mediating role of job stress and the moderating role of locus of control: Empirical evidence from the Vietnamese banking industry. *Cogent Business & Management, 7*(1), 1841359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1841359>
- Grant, S., & Ferris, K. (2012). Identifying sources of occupational stress in entrepreneurs for measurement. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Venturing, 4*(4), 351. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijev.2012.049828>
- Güzel, A., Samancı Tekin, Ç., & Uçan Yamaç, S. (2024). Exploring the impacts of perceived locus of control on post-traumatic stress disorder among disaster survivors: A systematic review. *Journal of psychiatric and mental health nursing, 31*(5), 776–787. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpm.13030>

- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2022). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)* (3rd Ed.). Sage: Thousand Oaks.
- Hilbrecht, M. (2016). Self-employment and experiences of support in a work–family context. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 28(1), 75–96. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08276331.2015.1117878>
- Huang, M., Wang, J., & Su, X. (2024). The impact of social support on entrepreneurial well-being: The role of entrepreneurial passion and entrepreneurial efficacy. *SAGE Open*, 14(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241297232>
- Igwe, P. A., Newbery, R., Amoncar, N., White, G. R., & Madichie, N. O. (2018). Keeping it in the family: exploring Igbo ethnic entrepreneurial behaviour in Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 26(1), 34–53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijebr-12-2017-0492>
- Karimi, R., & Alipour, F. (2011). Social support and job stress: moderation role of locus of control. *Journal of Asian Scientific Research*, 1(6), 285–290. <https://archive.aessweb.com/index.php/5003/article/download/3297/5308>
- Kaur, R. (2024). Influences of work stressors and family support: the mediating role of job performance. *Vilakshan – XIMB Journal of Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/xjm-09-2023-0196>
- Kiefl, S., Fischer, S., & Schmitt, J. (2024). Self-employed and stressed out? The impact of stress and stress management on entrepreneurs' mental health and performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1365489. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1365489>
- Kipkosgei, F. (2022). Perceived entrepreneurial stress and entrepreneurial resilience; the mediating role of the Well-Being of Entrepreneurs and moderating role perceived online social support. *Merits*, 2(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/merits2010001>
- Kock, N. (2015). Common method bias in PLS-SEM: A full collinearity assessment approach. *International Journal of e-Collaboration*, 11(4), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijec.2015100101>
- Krithiga, R., & Velmurugan, G. (2024). Examining the impact of stress and coping strategies on the performance of women entrepreneurs. *Multidisciplinary Reviews*, 7(7), 2024148. <https://doi.org/10.31893/multirev.2024148>
- Liu, S. (2020). The impact of social support on job stress of shift working mothers: a study of casino employees in Macao. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 11(3), 559–570. <https://doi.org/10.1108/aeds-02-2020-0037>
- Mahmoud, A. B., Reisel, W. D., Hack-Polay, D., & Fuxman, L. (2021). No one is safe! But who's more susceptible? Locus of control moderates pandemic perceptions' effects on job insecurity and psychosocial factors amongst MENA hospitality frontliners: a PLS-SEM approach. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-12071-2>
- Micheletto, V., Zito, M., Bustreo, M., Gabrielli, G., Circi, R., & Russo, V. (2022). The Impact of Optimism and Internal Locus of Control on Workers' Well-Being, A Multi-Group Model Analysis before and during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Social Sciences*, 11(12), 559. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci11120559>
- Nurlaili, F., Aini, E., & Asmoro, P. (2018). Does family social support affect startup business activities? *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 74(2), 41–54. <https://doi.org/10.18551/rjoas.2018-02.06>
- Ononye, U., Ofili, P., Ndudi, F., & Agbim, K. C. (2022). Family support, psychological capital, and start-up formation. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 20(1), 342–352. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.20\(1\).2022.28](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.20(1).2022.28)
- Ononye, U. H. (2022). Social support and new venture initiation with resilience as a mediating factor. *Enterprise Development and Microfinance*, 33(3), 170–181. <https://doi.org/10.3362/1755-1986.21-00046>
- Stevenson, C., Wakefield, J. R. H., Kellezi, B., Stack, R. J., & Dogra, S. (2021). Families as support and burden: A mixed methods exploration of the extent to which family identification and support predicts reductions in stress among disadvantaged neighbourhood residents. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 39(4), 886–907. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02654075211050071>
- Thomas, W. H. N., Sorensen, K. L., & Eby, L. T. (2006). Locus of control at work: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 27(8), 1057–1087. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.416>
- Tseng, T. H., Wang, Y., Lin, H., Lin, S., Wang, Y., & Tsai, T. (2022). Relationships between locus of control, theory of planned behavior, and cyber entrepreneurial intention: The moderating role of cyber entrepreneurship education. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 20(3), 100682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2022.100682>
- Uddin, M. (2021). The role of family social support on work stress for frontline working mothers in Bangladesh. *Studies in Business and Economics*, 23(1), 38–60. <https://doi.org/10.29117/sbe.2020.0120>

- Ugwu, F. O., Ugwu, C., Njemanze, V. C., & Nwosu, I. (2018). Family cohesion and family size moderating burnout and recovery connection. *Occupational Medicine*, 69(1), 28–34. <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmed/kqy155>
- VanderZee, K. I., Buunk, B. P., & Sanderman, R. (1997). Social support, locus of control, and psychological Well-Being. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 27(20), 1842–1859. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.1997.tb01628.x>
- Williams, A. (1985). Stress and the entrepreneurial role. *International Small Business Journal Researching Entrepreneurship*, 3(4), 11–25. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026624268500300401>
- Wu, F., Ren, Z., Wang, Q., He, M., Xiong, W., Ma, G., Fan, X., Guo, X., Liu, H., & Zhang, X. (2020). The relationship between job stress and job burnout: the mediating effects of perceived social support and job satisfaction. *Psychology Health & Medicine*, 26(2), 204–211. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13548506.2020.1778750>